

TRANSFORMING THE PRIMARY MATHEMATICS CURRICULUM: GUIDING PERSPECTIVES

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INTRODUCTION

In 2014 two research reports were published by the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA) to underpin the redeveloped mathematics curriculum for 3–8 year olds (Dooley, Dunphy, Shiel, et al., 2014; Dunphy, Dooley, Shiel, et al., 2014). Recently an addendum to the research reports was published, its aim being to give consideration to aspects of these reports that need particular emphasis or amendment for older primary children (Dooley, 2019). Here the guiding perspectives for the upcoming Primary Mathematics Curriculum (PMC) as proposed in the research reports and the addendum (referred to collectively as ‘the research reports’ hereafter) are outlined. Some implications of these perspectives for curriculum are discussed. In this discussion I adopt the understanding of mathematics curriculum proposed by Remillard and Heck (2014), that is “*a plan for the experiences* that learners will encounter, as well as the *actual experiences* they do encounter, that are designed to help them reach specified mathematics objectives” (p.707, italics in original).

GUIDING PERSPECTIVES

The research reports endorse an equitable curriculum in which all children have access to mathematics. Equitable access to mathematics is dependent on perspectives on mathematics and how it is learnt. In particular, a view of mathematics as ‘absolute and certain’ is often regarded as eliminating learners from the discipline whereas a view of mathematics as cultural and context-dependent is more aligned with inclusion. In the research reports, it is proposed that the new mathematics curriculum should be premised on a view of mathematics espoused by Hersh (1997), that is, “mathematics as a human activity, a social phenomenon, part of human culture, historically evolved, and intelligible only in a social context” (p.xi). Such a view has important implications for how mathematics is learnt and taught. Sociocultural theories of learning, in which both the social aspects as well as cultural influences are seen as centrally important to learning, are germane to Hersh’s definition above. However, it is acknowledged in the research reports that learning is generally considered to be a complex process not easily explained by a single theory or perspective. Other theories identified as relevant to the teaching, learning and assessment of mathematics are cognitive theories including constructivism in which the construction of knowledge by the individual is emphasised; and social-constructivism which takes account of the central role of social interaction in shaping an individual’s learning. As will be seen below, the extent to which these various theories are foregrounded has considerable influence on the planned-for and actual experiences embodied in the PMC.

IMPLICATIONS FOR THE PRIMARY MATHEMATICS CURRICULUM

Construction of the curriculum

An implication of the view of mathematics outlined above is that in the planning and actualization of the PMC, teachers have to take account of learners' interests, backgrounds and ways of knowing. As pupils interact with mathematical tasks, with each other and with the teacher, they contribute to the construction of the curriculum at a local level. As suggested by Remillard and Heck (2014, p.716), "[the curriculum] cannot be fully predesigned and involves design work in the moment." Thus the PMC is dynamic and evolving in nature, and learners have a central role in its construction.

Big Ideas

Big ideas in children's mathematical learning are seen, especially in the US, as crucial to the development of children's mathematical understanding. These ideas are often conflated with curriculum goals. While it is generally accepted that these ideas connect various concepts and procedures within and across domains, there is less agreement on what these big ideas might be. From a cognitivist perspective, the focus of big ideas is on content (e.g., 'adding and subtracting') whereas from a sociocultural perspective, there is a greater emphasis on processes (e.g., 'argumentation'). Arising from the view of mathematics and the learning of mathematics delineated above, both content and processes deserve attention in the specification of goals in the PMC.

Learning Paths

Learning paths are the sequences that apply in a general way to children's development in the different mathematical domains. These are based on developmental progressions which have been constructed for a number of key aspects of mathematics, especially - in the context of early mathematics - by Clements and Sarama (2009). There are different approaches to the explication of learning paths. These include linear/nonlinear presentation, level of detail specified, mapping of paths to age/grade, and role of teaching. Different presentations of learning paths reflect different theoretical perspectives. In the research reports, a presentation of paths that is consistent with a sociocultural view of learning is promoted, that is, paths as provisional, not linked to age and arising from engagement in mathematically rich activity.

Features of Pedagogy

The teaching-learning relationship is at the heart of mathematics education. Pedagogy is regarded as a complex whole where elements related to teaching, learning, and the design of learning environments connect and interact. Features of good pedagogy related to (a) People and Relationships, (b) The Learning Environment and (c) The Learner, are listed in the research reports (although some of these are adapted in the addendum in recognition of the changing nature of 'play' for the older age group). The former two are aligned with sociocultural perspective while the third grouping is more commensurate with a cognitivist approach. This classification exemplifies the significance of co-ordinating learning theories in the planned-for and actual learning experiences in mathematics.

Final Remarks

It is well recognized that teachers play a crucial role in the interpretation and design of curriculum. However, according to Remillard (2012), teachers' interactions with curriculum resources are influenced by their past experience and assumptions about what it is to do and learn mathematics. She goes on to argue that curriculum resources should 'speak to' teachers and that curriculum materials should contribute to their learning. Given the impact of guiding perspectives on mathematics and mathematics learning on the PMC, it is vital that they receive adequate and prominent attention in these curriculum resources.

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